

IMPACT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE ON WORK LIFE BALANCE: AN INDIAN PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

The increase in work stress, globalization and advancement in technology has made work-life balance an issue with both the genders. Life includes various concerns like, career, wealth family, social commitment, health etc. A well balanced life for an employee needs a careful integration and sync between the stated quests and in maintaining this sync, the employee is left completely stressed. Almost every employee in organizations undergoes emotions such as fading trust, harsh uncertainty, strangled creativity, communication between bureaucrats and employees, and disappearing trustworthiness and responsibility. Thus, emotions have a great impact on our lives and so these emotions need to be thoroughly understood and managed. Therefore, Emotional Intelligence is the observant and watchful management of our own emotions. Its awareness and use can provide personal and interpersonal gain. Through Emotional Intelligence, the employees can enhance their creativity, emotional self-awareness, emotional expression, tolerance power, trust and may even have better and improved relations within and beyond the organization which in turn would help in enhancing the employee performance and the organization all together. It figures out the possibilities for gaining the practical skills which are based on its five components: motivation, self-awareness self-regulation, empathy, and adeptness in relationships. Emotional intelligence helps to improvise the performance of an individual and the organization as a whole. It also plays a vital role in the type of work an employee stimulates and the bond as well as the relationships a person enjoys within and outside the organization. This study attempts to analyse how Emotional Intelligence plays an influential role in balancing work and how it tends to improvise the Quality Work Life.

KEYWORDS: Emotional Intelligence (EI), Work Life Balance (WLB), Quality Work Life (QWL).

Introduction

Meaning of Emotion

Emotion can be described as "Any anxious or uproar of feelings, mind, passion, and any furious or hopped-up mental status."

According to Morris, C.G. (1979) emotion is a complex affective experience that involves diffuse physiological changes and can be expressed overtly in characteristic behaviour patterns.

Above definitions describes emotions as some kind of feelings or propelling experiences which are distinguished by some organic changes that broadly guide them to carry out some or the other types of course of conduct.

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Types of Emotions

According to Goleman, D.(1995), the types of emotions and some of their family members are as follows:

- **Anger**

Outrage, annoyance, offends, exasperation, disapprobation, indignation, displeasure, impatience, enmity, acrimony, irritability, hostility, fury, antagonism, hatred, resentment and violence.

- **Sadness**

Anguish, gloominess, poignancy, grief, sorrow, cheerlessness, cheerlessness, dismals, bleakness, melancholy, self-pity, loneliness, regrets, anxiety, dejection, despair and ruefulness when intense depression is caused.

- **Fear**

Worry, anxiety, panic, uneasiness apprehension, nervousness, cowardice, awe, timidity, agitation, apprehend, intimidation consternation, misgiving, dread, fright, terror result into psychological phobia and dismay.

- **Enjoyment**

Happiness, amusement, satisfaction, thrill, joy, relief, indulgence, fun, gratification contentment, bliss, delight, pride, pleasure, thrill, relish, bliss, cheer, zest, gladness euphoria and joyfulness.

- **Love**

Affection, attachment, regard, cherish, tenderness, acceptance, admiration, praise, relish, friendliness, trust, kindness, affection, tenderness, delight, affinity, fondness, zeal, adoration, and treasure.

- **Surprise**

Amazed, wonderment, perplex, astonishment, stunned, wonder.

- **Disgust**

Contempt, dislike, repel, offend, disdain, scorn, abhorrence, aversion, disrelish, scandalize.

- **Shame**

Dishonour, humiliation, ashamed, disconcert, disgraced, embarrassment, remorse, stigma, infamy, regrets.

Therefore, Emotions plays an important role in organising human experiences and so in the absence of them, life would be weary and would fall vacant. They also provides the inner driving force that either attracts a person or repels one person from another.

Emotional Intelligence

Emotional intelligence implies to the potential to recognise, manage and to analyse emotions. It enables employees to think in a creative manner and use their emotions wisely to solve problems.

Researchers propose that emotional intelligence can be understood and intensified while others argues that it is an ingrained attribute.

Emotional intelligence comprises of five attributes:

- Knowing one's emotions.
- Managing one's emotions.
- Motivating oneself.
- Recognizing other's emotions.
- Handling relationships.

Emotional intelligence (EI) enhances individual as well as organizational performance. An Emotionally stable and balanced worker possess the following traits of emotional intelligence:

- **Self-awareness**

People who possess high EI understands their emotions very well and they do not allow their feelings to overpower them.

- **Self-Regulation**

It is the ability to control one's emotions. People who self-regulate themselves think before they act and do not make careless decisions.

- **Motivation**

People who possess high EI are extremely constructive and energetic. They love to accept challenges and are highly productive in whatever they do.

- **Empathy**

It is the potential to analyse and identify the expectations, wants and needs of the people around us. Empathetic people always try not to judge too quickly. They live their lives in an honest way.

- **Social Skills**

People who possess strong social skills are team oriented. They have the ability to manage disputes and have the capability to build and maintain relations and communicate effectively.

Work- Life Balance

- **Meaning**

Work-life balance means the prioritisation or the division of the working and family or personal activities by an individual in his/her life. It is a state of equilibrium which demands equal time for personal, professional and family life respectively.

- **Definition**

"It is the potential of an employee to maintain a healthy balance between his/her work roles, personal responsibilities, and family life."

A poor balance between personal and professional life does not only affects the individuals but also the organisation they work for suffers.

Therefore, Work-Life Balance motivates the employees to allocate their time based on order of priorities and to devote time to health, family, vacations etc. along with focus on career.

Benefits of Work-Life Balance

- **To Employees**

- Improved personal and family relations.
- Improved on-the-job and off-the-job relations.
- Enhanced motivation, focus and job satisfaction.
- Improved health and wellbeing of employees.

- **To Organisation**

- Enhanced team work and communication.
- Lower absenteeism.
- Increased Productivity.
- A less stressed and happier workforce.

Impact of Emotional Intelligence on Work-Life Balance

- **Better and improved communal/social relations among adults:** Adults who perceive high emotional intelligence are likely to have better understanding of social ability and more blooming interpersonal relationships and they balance their work life effortlessly.
- **Higher emotional stability leads to higher social competence:** Individuals with high EI possess high social competence and tends to be more socialized, perceptive, and cordial to be around.
- **Strengthened family and work relationships:** High EI is indicates strengthened relationships with family and work partners to a great extent.
- **Satisfaction in life:** Higher Emotional Intelligence is vastly related with higher satisfaction towards life- low level of insecurity otherwise it is negatively correlated with poor health and behavioural pattern.

- **Promotes Healthy Work Life Balance (WLB):** Emotional intelligence helps in promoting healthy work life balance as it helps employees in prioritising their work and so an employee is in a state to devote equal time to his work and family.
- **Enhance Quality of Work Life (QWL):** High EI helps in enhancing the quality work life as it creates positive feeling towards the job. It is achieved when the employees are treated respectfully and with dignity. Such positivity not only meets the needs of an employee but of the organization too. This creates a sense of satisfaction within him/her which also has a direct impact on health. It therefore helps in maintaining physical as well as mental health, loyalty and trust towards the organization.

Conclusion

This study reflects that in this global liberalized world, Emotional Intelligence emerge as a prime cause of employee's stability, loyalty and retention. It seems that higher emotional stability leads to higher work life balance of employees. Emotional Intelligence is a valuable means to incorporate, strengthen and ensure better work and family life.

With the help of this study, it is concluded that emotional intelligence has a strong impact on the performance of employees which is based on a proper equilibrium between work, family and leisure.

Therefore, organisations globally should focus on formulation, implementation and maintaining better work-life balance policies so as to maintain a successful and sustainable organization. They should focus on building efficient and effective working culture and environment. This will in turn minimise the work stress, work related issues and grievances among the employees which results in the enhancement of Quality Work Life (QWL). Hence, the employees will get more time to focus on their productive work along with enhancing their own as well as organizational performance.

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